

EWA-BELT

Linking East and West African farming systems experience
into a BELT of sustainable intensification

Promoting remote real time crop health services to rural communities in West and East Africa: Remote PLANT HEALTH Diagnostic platform–Planthead

Practice Abstract n.3

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Promoting remote real time crop health services to rural communities in West and East Africa: Remote PLANT HEAlth Diagnostic platform–Planthead

Several partners of the EWA BELT project are contributing to the implementation of a PLANT HEAlth Diagnostic (PLANTHEAD) network in Africa, to promote real time diagnosis and environment–friendly crop protection approaches in resource–constrained environments lacking the organizational and/or the sociotechnical system resources to cope with crop health diseases. The network is based on the World Food and Health Security e–Center (HFSeC), and is based on Internet of Things, wearable technologies and mobile devices. The proposed approach conjugates the adoption of low cost, high throughput technologies with a web–based service for farmers, extension, and local research personnel to enable and facilitate: 1) social networking, 2) participation, 3) apo mediation, 4) openness, and 5) collaboration, within and between user groups. Valorization of traditional knowledge, involvement of local actors, and technology appropriation will increase the likelihood of success of the PLANTHEAD network. The shared database represents an extremely valuable tool for epidemiological studies, as it generates interactive georeferenced maps, thereby allowing real–time monitoring, modelling, and forecasting the progression of a pathogen or any pest that may raise serious food security/safety concern in the area. An artificial intelligence is being trained to recognize and identify the most common foliar diseases on groundnut, a crop that has been unanimously listed as the most grown by the partners in the involved sub–Saharan countries.

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Promuovere servizi per la salute delle colture da remoto in tempo reale nelle comunità rurali dell'Africa occidentale e orientale: piattaforma Planthead

Diversi partner del progetto EWA BELT stanno contribuendo all'implementazione di una rete "PLANT HEalth Diagnostic" (PLANTHEAD) in Africa, per promuovere la diagnosi in tempo reale di patogeni che colpiscono le colture alimentari e diffondere misure di protezione rispettose dell'ambiente in contesti con risorse limitate e privi di servizi. La rete si basa sul World Food and Health Security e-Center (HFSeC) e sull' Internet of Things, tecnologie accessibili e dispositivi mobili. L'approccio proposto coniuga l'adozione di tecnologie a basso costo e ad alto rendimento, con un servizio basato sul web rivolto ad agricoltori, extension agents e personale di ricerca locale al fine di facilitare: 1) social networking, 2) partecipazione, 3) apo mediazione, 4) apertura e 5) collaborazione, all'interno e tra gruppi di utenti. La valorizzazione delle conoscenze tradizionali, il coinvolgimento degli attori locali e l'appropriazione della tecnologia aumenteranno le probabilità di successo della rete PLANTHEAD. Il database condiviso rappresenta uno strumento estremamente prezioso per gli studi epidemiologici, in quanto genera mappe georeferenziate interattive, consentendo in tal modo il monitoraggio, la modellazione e la previsione in tempo reale della progressione di un agente patogeno o di qualsiasi organismo nocivo che può causare seri problemi di sicurezza alimentare nell'area. In questa fase, un'intelligenza artificiale si sta progressivamente definendo per riconoscere e identificare le malattie fogliari più comuni sull'arachide, coltura che è stata unanimemente indicata come la più coltivata dai partner nei paesi subsahariani coinvolti.

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